

Compositional Strategies to Create Experiences of Imaginary Spaces through Headphone Listening

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Abstract. The study aims to find effective compositional strategies for creating experiences of imaginary spaces through headphone listening, which can be used as a descriptive tool during composing. The compositional strategies are discussed under the framework, structured as four interrelated elements: composing the narrative, environment, movement, and structure.

The study will begin by identifying different types of imaginary spaces evoked by sound compositions, investigating compatible software instruments for enhancing spatial imagery through headphones. This study is an example of the use of headphones in electroacoustic spatial music, with the aim of creating more accessible and affordable immersive listening experiences.

Is it possible to direct each listener's spatial imagination at a significant level? Do the differences in spatial thinking ability and spatial vocabulary extent of the listener influence their experience? To answer these questions, a methodology was developed consisting of a theoretical foundation (descriptive tool), a practical implementation (composition) and the observation of users' experiences through surveys (listening experiment).

The composition created using this tool was evaluated in controlled sessions with participants trained in sound and/or spatial design. Listeners provided yes/no responses, scaled ratings, and open-ended comments. In the first stage, they listened with eyes closed to assess general impressions; in the second, they detailed spatial and compositional elements. Three-stage interviews yielded both quantitative and qualitative insights. Results show that the composition successfully generated immersive and spatially rich experiences. Overall, the findings support the effectiveness of the proposed strategies and validate the research method's capacity to measure the perceptibility of abstract spatial works.

Keywords: imaginary space · perception of space · spatial audio · sound art · headphone listening · electroacoustic music.

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Proc. of the 17th Int. Symposium on Computer Music Multidisciplinary Research, London, United Kingdom, 2025

1 Introduction

How do listeners perceive spaces, whether physical or imaginary? Although our perception of space is multisensory and dominated by vision, the contribution of listening is undeniable. Pallasmaa (2005) emphasizes that hearing plays a fundamental role in structuring and articulating our experience of space. Sound provides the temporal continuum that gives visual impressions coherence and vitality; without it, spatial perception loses its sense of continuity and life (p. 49).

The study's main goal, in its simplest form, is to develop a spatial experience that is guided only by hearing, like virtual reality (VR) but only for the ears.

There is no doubt that electroacoustic music¹ has the potential to stimulate the mind of the listener to imagine spaces. There are imaginary spaces in the listener's mind that evoke and change with listening to the compositions. As Andean (2016) puts it, these spaces have unstable features: "...as a stream of spaces...telling a story of imaginative, constantly shifting spaces." (p. 198).

According to the previous investigation, there is no artistic approach to binaural audio in electroacoustic music. Therefore, the aim is to use it to create spatial experiences and propose a new application area for binaural audio that goes beyond games, VR, and other entertainment areas. Also, there are few applications for narrative spatialization in headphone listening as opposed to multiple loudspeaker setups. Binaural audio technology², perceptual spatial audio format for headphones, however, can provide more accessible and affordable immersive listening experiences, thus my research aims to explore ways to build these experiences by presenting detailed built environments, fluidity in spatial changes, and holistic narratives.

The main research question is: What are effective compositional tools and strategies for creating an experience of a journey into imaginary spaces through headphone listening? The questions then follow: Are these imaginary spaces perceptible to each listener? Is it possible to direct the spatial imagination of each listener to a significant level? Do differences in spatial thinking ability and the extent of spatial vocabulary of the listener influence their experience?

To answer these questions, a methodology was developed consisting of a theoretical foundation with the conceptual framework forming a descriptive tool (a review and compilation of previous studies and new suggestions), a practical implementation (a composition entitled SPATCHES), and observation of the user experiences through qualitative surveys (listening experiment).

¹ "Music in which electronic technology, now primarily computer-based, is used to access, generate, explore and configure sound materials, and in which loudspeakers are the prime medium of transmission." (Emmerson & Smalley, 2008, p. 1).

² "Binaural audio reproduction techniques take advantage of the human natural spatial auditory cues to recreate a virtual auditory environment through headphones or loudspeakers that emulate headphone reproduction." (Geluso & Roginska, 2017, p. 3).

2 Descriptive Tool

The inductive approach was used to review all the compositional strategies and create a framework considering their role in the construction of the spatial experience. The framework is structured as four interrelated elements: composing the narrative, environment, motion, and structure. Each element is interconnected and individually important as Bateson (1979) notes that:

The aggregate is something more than the sum of the parts because the combining of the parts is not a simple adding but it is the nature of multiplication or fractionation or the creation of a logical product. A momentary gleam of enlightenment. (Bateson, 1979, as cited in Doombusch, 2006, p. 2)

The first element, the narrative, provides relationships and continuum between each sound unit on different scales to enhance the listeners' engagement with the composition. The second element, the environment provides a detailed and well-defined environment with interactivity in perspective and depth for the sense of being in an all-encompassing bigger place (urban scale/outdoor). The third element, the motion provides mobility of the listener and surroundings (object scale). The fourth element, the structure provides the creation of geometrical structures and spatial narrative for the sense of being in smaller enclosed spaces (building scale/indoor). Table 1 presents a comprehensive overview of the roles of each element and the corresponding domains of referential studies.

Table 1. Interrelated Elements, Roles, and Referential Areas

Element	Roles and Referential Areas
Narrative	-relationships and continuity between each sound unit in different scales -sense of engagement for the listener #electroacoustic music
Environment	-detailed setting with variety in perspective and depth -sense of being in places, with depth, and interactivity -outdoor/urban scale #soundscape #soundwalk
Motion	-mobility of the listener and surroundings -sense of motion and mobility -object scale #electroacoustic music #soundwalk
Structure	-setting the spatial properties (corners, boundaries, size, gaps, materials, and units.) -creating geometrical structures -creating spatial impressions (entering the space, transformation of the space, overlapping of the different spaces, crossing rooms, etc.) -sense of being in spaces, plasticity, and transition. -indoor/building scale #sound sculpture #electroacoustic music

3 Composition

SPATCHES was composed as the practical outcome of the research and served as a tool to evaluate the user experience regarding the effectiveness of the strategies and tools developed throughout the theoretical study. The sounds were recorded in the author's grandmother's village and in her deteriorating house, which the author never had the chance to experience (see Fig. 1). The goal was to document and transform this house through sound, creating a memory in a place previously unfamiliar. This link contains the audio. (<https://youtu.be/PPh3Yc4Oc30>)

Everyday household objects and materials (such as light switches, curtains, doors, walls, and windows) were recorded using a Zoom H6 digital sound recorder with two angled cardioid microphones (90 degrees) in stereo format. Two channels were generally used, while only one was used when necessary. All sound scenes were reproduced through binaural processing in Ableton Live 10.1.1, a digital audio workstation (DAW) for music creation and performance (Ableton, 2025), using the Envelop for Live (E4L) plug-in, an open-source toolkit for spatial audio production (Envelop, 2025). The output was binaural, with static rendering and no head tracking.

Fig. 1. Recording environment (The author's grandmother's village house)

After testing several plug-ins, including SPAT, Anaglyph, and dearVR PRO by Sennheiser, E4L was selected as the most suitable tool for its accessibility and comprehensive features. The narrative aimed to sustain emotional engagement rather than full comprehension, while spatial impressions and strategies (Table 2) were designed for clear perception, as illustrated in the author's graphic score. (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Graphic score of SPATCHES

Table 2. Scenes and spatial impressions used in SPATCHES

Scenes	Spatial Impressions and Strategies
Scene 1: The Village [00':00"-00':10"]	-Composing the Environment (locating the objects, living things, incidents in the environment) -getting closer to the enclosed space -entering the space -blending interior and outdoor
Scene 2: The House [00':10"- 01':12"]	-Composing the Structure (setting the corners, boundaries, size, gaps, materials, units, objects.) -pinpointing corners (momentary sounds) -scanning surfaces -filling the entire volume of a space -Composing the Motion (mobility of the objects and listener) -standing still and observing the surroundings in the space -wandering in the space -being aware of other rooms in the space -crossing rooms in the space -blending different rooms -blending different times (memories and present)
Scene 3: The Leakages [01':12"- 01':50"]	-transformation of the space -sudden change of the space
Scene 4: The Dispersion [01':50"- 02':40"]	-overlapping of the different spaces
Scene 5: The Demolition [02':40"- 03':11"]	-the collapse of the space

4 Listening Experiment

The listening experiments were conducted under COVID-19 conditions at the MIAM (Centre for Advanced Music Studies) Library, Istanbul Technical University, using studio headphones (Beyerdynamic DT-770 Pro, 80 ohm) and CD players (TASCAM CD-A500). To provide a controlled experiment, the test environment and equipment had to be the same for everyone. With this setup, up to four participants were able to listen simultaneously. All 22 participants, who were able to see the test environment, were categorized into four representative groups according to their backgrounds. Each group includes at least five participants as a combination of sound design and spatial design training. The listening groups and numbers of the participants are as follows:

- subjects trained in spatial design: five respondents (22.73%),
- subjects trained in sound design: six respondents (27.27%),
- subjects trained both in spatial design and in sound design: six respondents (27.27%),
- subjects trained neither in spatial design nor in sound design: five respondents (22.73%).

The listening experiment consisted of three stages. The first stage included listening to the composition for the first time with eyes closed, followed by yes/no or scaling questions on the respondents' general spatial impressions. The second stage involved listening to the composition for the second time with eyes open, having read the questions before listening intended to gather more details. The third stage, without listening, involved the respondents answering open-ended questions and providing general feedback.

Limiting the respondent's answer by yes/no and rating scale questions is a way to gather more quantitative data, and to achieve more revealing and meaningful results in perceptual experiments. Other studies of perceptual experiments, from Macedo (2014) and Fuentes & Schumacher (2017), were used as reference during the preparation of the questions, and the evaluation of the results. Percentages for each answer were calculated both for each listening group and for the total. In this way, both the general picture can be commented on and the situation within the group can be observed. Also, the differences between groups can be observed by making comparisons across the answers.

The consistency of the answers was scaled according to the percentage of "yes" responses, or the sum of "strong" and "very strong" impressions for the rating scale questions. Results were marked as highly consistent when above 90%, very consistent between 80–90%, consistent between 70–80%, less consistent but still remarkable between 60–70%, not so remarkable between 50–60%, and not remarkable below 50%. Finally, a quantitative and qualitative analysis of the responses was made.

4.1 First Stage

The first stage included the listening to the composition for the first time with eyes closed, focusing only on what they heard, before reading any questions.

They then answered the questions after the listening; yes/no questions or scaling questions on general impressions of imaginary spaces, spatial parameters, such as distance, direction, and motion. The first question of the first stage was rating scale question and intended to investigate whether the listeners had the impression of other places than the listening space, and the degree of their impressions by expecting them to rate them a scale from weak (1) to very strong (4). Table 3 summarizes the answers to the first question of the first stage. It shows spatial designers' respondents had the strongest impression of other places, while sound designers is less consistent but still remarkable responses.

Table 3. Answers to the first question of the first stage. (Have you had the impression of other places than the listening space? To what degree do you have the impression of other places?)

Respondents	Spatial designers	Sound designer	Both	None
22 resp.	5 resp.(22,73%)	6 resp.(27,27%)	6 resp.(27,27%)	5 resp.(22,73%)
4:very strong	5(100,00%)	1 (16,67%)	4 (66,67%)	4(80,00%)
3:strong	-	3 (50,00%)	2 (33,33%)	1 (20,00%)
2:less strong	-	1 (16,67%)	-	-
1:weak	-	1 (16,67%)	-	-

The first question also asked the participants to list the spaces they imagined while listening to the composition. Most listeners imagined similar indoor and outdoor spaces similar to those were intended. The answers show that the most common perceptions of space were produced by the referential sounds. Table 4 summarizes the respondents' imaginary spaces. The answers were grouped as five spaces: indoor/domestic spaces, indoor/workshop spaces, outdoor/urban spaces, outdoor/natural spaces, and surreal spaces. The most common answers for indoor/domestic spaces are either "house" or "cabin", some respondents gave also material detail of their imaginary spaces "wooden house/cabin". Other common answers regarding imaginary spaces are "workshop", "street", and "seashore", all answers which were consistent with my expectations.

Table 4. Answers to the first question of the first stage.

Groups of spaces	Answers
Indoor/domestic spaces	"house"; "wooden cabin", "shelter", "barn", "corridor", "old house hall", "a tiled room", "attic," "stairs".
Indoor/workshop spaces	"warehouse", "factory", "workshop".
Outdoor/urban spaces	"street", "marketplace", "highway", "train track", "port".
Outdoor/natural spaces	"seashore", "under the water stream", "under the cliffs", "garden", "desolate field".
Surreal spaces	"very small space", "inside the jar", "inside the body".

The second question of the first stage was rating scale question and intended to investigate whether the listeners perceived the spatial parameters (distance, direction, and motion), and the degree of their impressions by having them rate it on a scale from weak impression (1) to very strong impression (4). The most consistent answer is for the sounds moving in space. Distances had less consistent but still remarkable answers. Table 5 summarizes the answers to the second question of the first stage. Looking at all the groups for these three impressions, the most consistent affirmative answers are from the spatial designers' group.

Table 5. Answers to the second question of the first stage. (Have you had any impressions for the following spatial parameters?)

Spatial Parameters	Results
Motion	highly consistent
Direction	very consistent
Distance	less consistent, but still quite remarkable
Moving objects	highly consistent
Being in motion	not so remarkable

The question examined whether the listeners had the impression of moving objects or of being in motion, and the degree of these impressions. The results indicate that the composition needs further development in terms of mobilizing the listener. Some respondents reported that they did not feel being in motion because, in the physical world, they were sitting still in a chair while listening. The test conditions and environment might also have influenced this outcome.

4.2 Second Stage

The second stage involved listening to the composition for the second time with eyes open, having read the questions before listening. They then answered the questions during the listening, which are yes/no questions or scaling questions on more detailed impressions of the properties of the imaginary space, the way they experience the space, the way they perceive the space, and the elements of the composition.

The first question of the second stage was a yes/no question which examined whether listeners perceived various spatial properties in Scene 2: The House [00':10"-01':12"]. Table 6 summarizes the results as size, materials, and life received highly consistent responses; boundaries were very consistent; while gaps, objects, and units were less consistent but still notable. The least consistent responses were related to corners and form (5.55%), likely due to the inclusion of two distinct properties in one question. Across groups, the highest consistency was observed among spatial designers and cross-disciplinary designers, followed by non-designers; the sound designers group showed less consistent but still noteworthy results.

The results suggest that listeners more consistently perceive basic and prominent spatial properties, such as size, materials, and life, while more complex or composite properties, like corners and form, are harder to evaluate reliably. Additionally, participants with design-related backgrounds demonstrated higher perceptual consistency, indicating that prior spatial training or experience enhances the ability to detect and interpret spatial cues in auditory compositions.

Table 6. Answers to the first question of the second stage. (Have you had any impressions for the following properties of the space?)

Spatial Properties	Results
Size (95.45%) Materials (wood, steel, glass) (95.45%) Life (programme and users) (90.91%)	highly consistent
Boundaries (surfaces such as: wall, floor, ceiling) (86.36%)	very consistent
Gaps and location of the gaps (door, window) (63.64%) Objects and locations of the objects (furniture) (63.64%) Different units (rooms) (63.64%)	less consistent, but still quite remarkable
Corners and form (54.55%)	not so remarkable

The second question of the second stage was yes/no question and intended to investigate whether the listeners had the possible spatial impressions across the scenes in the composition in Table 2 within each group. The results are compatible with my expectations, such as the most consistent answers are from the spatial design trained related groups. In general, the less consistent answers are for the impressions intended to be given less in the composition. Also, the impressions such as “sense of collapse of the space” and “sense of construction of the space” are the terms that can be subjective. Table 7 summarizes the consistency of spatial perception across the five scenes. In Scene 1: The Village [00:00–00:10’], the sense of entering the space showed very consistent responses, while getting closer to the enclosed space was not so remarkable. In Scene 2: The House [00:10’–01:12’], observing the surroundings was very consistent, construction of the space was less remarkable, and wandering, awareness of other rooms, and crossing rooms were less consistent, but still quite remarkable. Scene 3: The Leakages [01:12’–01:50’] revealed highly consistent results for transformation and consistent results for sudden change. In Scene 4: The Dispersion [01:50’–02:40’], overlapping different spaces was very consistent, while in Scene 5: The Demolition [02:40’–03:11’], collapse of the space was not so remarkable. Among the five scenes, Scene 3: The Leakages was perceived most consistently, followed by Scene 1: The Village and Scene 4: The Dispersion, with Scene 2: The House showing moderate consistency, and Scene 5: The Demolition being the least consistently perceived.

The third question of the second stage was a rating scale question and asked for observing the most noticeable element for each group according to its appearance in this composition. These elements are the keystones of the literature

Table 7. Answers to the second question of the second stage. (Have you had any of the following spatial impressions?)

Spatial Impressions	Results
Sense of transformation of the space (95.45%))	highly consistent
Sense of entering the space (86.36%)	very consistent
Sense of observing the surroundings in the space (86.36%)	
Sense of overlapping of the different spaces (81.82%)	consistent
Sense of sudden change of the space (77.27%)	
Sense of wandering in the space (68.18%)	less consistent, but still quite remarkable
Sense of crossing rooms in the space (63.64%)	
Sense of being aware of other rooms in the space (63.64%)	
Sense of exiting the space (63.64%)	
Sense of moving away from the space (54.55%)	not so remarkable
Sense of collapse of the space (54.55%)	
Sense of getting closer to the enclosed space (50.00%)	
Sense of construction of the space (40.91%)	not remarkable

review and conceptual framework. Table 8 summarizes the answers to the third question. The sense of spatiality received the highest consistency, with around 80% of respondents reporting a very strong impression. Detailed environment and mobility were also prominent, each with roughly 55% very strong impressions. Interactivity showed consistent responses (40% very strong impressions), while the sense of narrative and plasticity were less noticeable for most listeners.

Table 8. Answers to the third question of the second stage. (Can you rate each element according to its appearance in this composition?)

Compositional Elements	Results
Sense of spatiality (acoustics, distance, etc.)	highly consistent
Sense of detailed environment (objects and creatures at different distances)	
Sense of mobility (movement of objects and listener)	very consistent
Sense of interactivity (changing perspective and focal points)	consistent
Sense of plasticity (sound as a sculptural material)	less consistent, but still quite remarkable
Sense of narrative (story)	

4.3 Third Stage

The third stage was made without listening to the composition. It includes the commentary questions on general feedback of the respondents intended to observe the familiarity and continuity in their experience. The questions in this stage are prepared with the reference to Fuentes and Schumacher’s (2017) perceptual experiment questions. The first two questions were open-ended questions,

intended to investigate the emotional engagement or estrangement in the experience of the listener. The third question was an open-ended question, intended to investigate the most memorable and familiar aspects of their experience.

The answers to the first question, which asks for the emotions that the listeners felt during the listening, complimented my expectations. In the beginning, they felt positive emotions, such as “belonging” possibly because of the familiarity of the sonic world, “feeling of being in shelter”, and “curiosity”. Then, with changes in the sonic world and chaotic auditory scenes, they started to feel negative emotions, such as “chaos” and “fear”. Some listeners reported bodily experiences like, while the others felt like an “observer”, so there is no need to worry. One respondent, in response to the chaotic auditory scenes, described the feeling of “disappearance and fragmentation”. This was my exact intention while composing the narrative and piece. Even the negative feelings show that most of the listeners felt emotionally engaged with the composition and that was my expectation and intention to build continuity in the experience of the listener. Table 9 summarizes the answers to this question.

Table 9. Answers to the first question of the third stage. (What emotions have you felt while listening to this fragment?)

Groups of feelings	Answers
Positive feelings	“belonging”, “feeling of being in shelter”, and “curiosity”.
Negative feelings	“chaos”, “fear”, and “disappearance and fragmentation”.
Feelings that refer to bodily experiences	“feeling of being trapped inside your own body”, “claustrophobia”, “feeling of your own body growing”, “feeling of being in a coma”.

Reported estrangement points for the second question were mainly related to crowded auditory scenes and changes in the perception of reality (materials and settings). Some respondents noted that sounds appeared close in both horizontal and vertical planes, possibly linked to the “inside-the-head locatedness”³ phenomenon. The third open-ended question, aimed at identifying the most memorable aspects of the experience, elicited references to familiar media such as “radio theatre” or “movie/murder investigation,” as well as auditory features like “foley without visual” or “electroacoustic foley.” Participants also described experiences of being in “another world,” “a dream,” “REM sleep,” “a memory,” or “someone else’s mind.” The most striking responses included “visiting another town just by listening,” “visualizing the story in the mind with sound,” “VR without visual,” and “journey,” reflecting the study’s initial conceptual keywords.

³ “All sounds tend to be perceived as coming from inside the head.” (Roginska, 2017, p. 91)

5 Conclusion

The test results are consistent with my expectations. Both the impression scores (derived by the answers to the yes/no and scaling questions) and the comments made on the open questions reveal that, to a considerable extent, the strategies achieved the desirable effects. The listeners' definitions and word choices used to describe their experiences mostly match keywords from my study since its inception; terms such as the feeling of being "on a journey, in a dream, or just... somewhere else", the sense of "visiting another town just by listening", and "through sound alone, being able to visualize the story in the mind". These descriptions show that the participants had experiences of imaginary spaces derived by narrative and motion aspects. Additionally, a considerable amount of the listeners reported having bodily experiences, a sign that they had a true sense of presence and immersive experiences.

In general, the answers to the yes/no and scaling questions show that the groups of spatial designers and designers of both areas had stronger impressions, then the non-designer group counterparts. The sound designers displayed somewhat less consistent but still remarkable answers for most of the impressions. This probably goes to show that the spatial thinking ability, and spatial vocabulary extent of the listener can influence their experience. It might also show that the sound designers' group displayed more critical listening. To be clear, it is important for future studies to detect the listener's listening mood through surveys.

Not only during the composition process, but also in the test questions, the terminology I used may have been more familiar to participants from architectural backgrounds. For future studies, to ensure that participants from sound design disciplines can also understand the concepts clearly, it would be beneficial to use the Spatial Audio Quality Inventory (SAQI), which provides a consensus vocabulary for the perceptual assessment of virtual acoustic environments (Lindau et al., 2014).

The results indicate that listeners most consistently perceived prominent and dynamic spatial features, such as spatiality, size, materials, life, and moving sounds, while more complex or composite properties, like corners, form, gaps, and units, as well as static or collapsing scenes, were less consistently perceived. Scenes emphasizing entry, observation, and transformation (e.g., Scene 3: The Leakages and Scene 1: The Village) were particularly effective in directing spatial imagination. Participants with design-related backgrounds demonstrated higher consistency, suggesting that spatial thinking ability and familiarity with spatial vocabulary enhance auditory spatial perception. Emotional engagement further supports this, as listeners reported both positive and negative responses, indicating sustained attention and immersion. Future studies could improve perceptual consistency by using dynamic and referential sounds, separating complex spatial features into distinct tasks, and tailoring auditory cues to participants' spatial experience. Overall, it is possible to guide each listener's spatial imagination, but the effectiveness depends on sound design, scene structure, and individual spatial skills.

There are some sides of the study and composition that need to be more efficient and developed for further studies. It would be efficient for future studies to be calm/regulated at certain points. The calm/regulated scenes can be built by clarifying focal points and simplifying the scenes. Also, it would be better to consider not to blur the perception of reality or change it in a way without arousing suspicion in the audience. To reduce the effect of inside-the-head locatedness phenomena, simplifying the auditory scenes and making the acoustic attributes clearer can be helpful. To enhance the sense of being in motion, adding more sounds for the movement (steps, breathings) and adding more orientations within the space can be useful. Also, it can show the strategy “giving movement to the character can result similarly in giving movement to the objects and perspectives” is ineffective. It would be better to give movements especially for the character for future studies.

In addition to improvements in composition and test conditions, head tracking offers mobility and interactivity, and its integration with VR environments can create virtual installations, allowing each listener to experience the auditory scene from different positions.

All in all, the aim of the study is developing compositional strategies to create experiences of imaginary spaces. The headphone listening of the electroacoustic compositions created by the descriptive tool delivers accessible and affordable immersive listening experiences. The study is also an attempt to find an alternative approach to both spatial and sound design.

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